

AESTHETIC PERCEPTION IS A PRODUCT OF ARTISTIC THINKING

Qurbonova Barchinoy Mirzakhamdamovna

Philosophy doctor (PhD), Ferghana state university

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Abstract. *In this article, aesthetic perception is a product of artistic thinking information is provided.*

Keywords: *perception, emotional-aesthetic, artistic-aesthetic, thinking, image, abstract, logical, induction, deduction.*

Artistic thinking is tasks, finding ways to solve them, defining actions (synthesis, analysis, generalization, abstraction and concretization).

It is important to use all types of thinking:

- clear practical thinking based on the direct perception of the work of art;
- visual-image thinking reflected in imagination;
- abstract theoretical thinking related to solving theoretical problems and the logic of artistic-aesthetic perception (analysis).

Artistic thinking is a type of bright image thinking aimed at materializing the artistic idea of a work of art. The pictorial representation of this idea is nothing more than a specific artistic-aesthetic activity of the perceiving person.

Thinking, especially artistic thinking, is an important factor of mental, spiritual and general artistic-aesthetic development. According to O.M. Jabborova, "in the process of intellectual development, artistic perception, students' qualities such as curiosity, diligence, agility and mobility, logical and critical thinking develop and improve, in general, the personality develops. In addition to the mentioned qualities, through artistic thinking, a person's life experience improves, the scope of his interests expands, his feelings increase (emotional-aesthetic), they deepen, the level of thinking increases (they become more perfect), his will is strengthened, his mental culture grows significantly, his mental activity is activated (striving for knowledge in the field of art; being able to see novelty, uniqueness, wonder, understanding its essence, understanding and distinguishing the main, important; not only artistic perception, but also using various types of operations in the practice of thinking in general)".

Thus, artistic thinking requires knowledge about art, about its specific type. Artistic thinking begins directly with the emotional perception of a work of art. There will certainly be an element of judgment in it. The central link of artistic thinking - logical-analytical thinking is formed.

At the same time, artistic thinking serves as a guiding tool for increasing the level of theoretical and practical knowledge of the perceiver.

Scientific methodical sources, analyzes of the state of art education practice, as for the level of features of artistic thinking, became the basis for determining the following quality indicators:

- emotional-psychological perception;
- intellectual - artistic-analytical thinking, evaluation at the level of generalized "seeing ability" (requirement);

such as evaluation of emotional-psychological interest, desire, positive attitude, emotional sensitivity, volitional readiness.

Thus, artistic thinking consists in the imaginative development of all components of an artistic work by materializing its ideological and artistic content.

In our example, the term element (French element, Latin elementum-complex and a part of the whole, a part of the system) is the components of the artistic thinking that is formed in the students, and each element performs its unique function, and the content and interpretation are integrated to form the elements of the whole artistic thinking.

Studies conducted by many scientists show that about 30% of schoolchildren develop stable interests in elementary grades. The task of the teacher is to determine the interests of students as early as possible. Also, the main goal is to create conditions for the harmonious development of the human personality in all aspects. "The created conditions also consist of different components, each of which has priority in the formation of one or another element of the artistic thinking formed in the student. "

Students of the upper grades are taught to acquire the methods of induction and deduction, rely on observations and experiments, and independently search for the causes of events. In other words, correct answers to the questions "Why is this?" it is required to explain that. As a result, students learn to use observations, examples, facts, and evidence. Undoubtedly, the elements of artistic thinking acquired in the "Fine Art" classes in grades 1-7 play an important role in the student's achievement of this level.

These mental activities help to develop artistic thinking in high school students.

Pupils will have the opportunity to master knowledge, skills and competences in terms of activities and their organization based on their age and personal psychological aspects. The age and psychological characteristics of students in this period create a basis for the decision to test their abilities to work in certain areas, to demonstrate their strength in various fields, including artistic creativity, and to demonstrate self-confidence.

It is known from the results of research conducted in the field of psychology that students of adolescent age have a strong desire to observe, understand the essence of the events taking place in the social life, express a personal attitude towards them, and evaluate them.

Adolescents begin to seek to find their place in life, unlike elementary school students, who develop a desire to study a particular work of art. They strive to actively participate in social processes, demonstrate their personal capabilities, and in most cases show examples of courage and bravery. However, the process of developing a romantic attitude towards the environment, social events and people is complicated by the desire to show examples of energetic energy, courage, bravery and heroism in teenagers. The fact that they do not have enough *life* experience, overestimating their knowledge in most cases causes them to make certain mistakes.

Adolescent age is called "transition period" and "difficult age period" in psychology. During this period, they begin to make initial efforts to find their place in social life. He begins to participate as a subject with personal views and opinions in the process of relationships organized in the family environment, the circle of peers and the microenvironment to which he belongs. However, in most cases, due to some physiological changes occurring in the adolescent's body, "some incomprehensible circumstances" occurring in their psyche, they tend to be more in the circle of their peers. They begin to withdraw from communication with adults. One of the factors that cause this situation is the fact that the teenager feels like an adult, demands that adults stop

treating him as if he is still a child, and the conflicts that arise due to the fact that adults are against such an idea. Therefore, in the life of a teenager, first of all, the microenvironment to which he belongs begins to take a leading place. In this process, it is necessary to pay special attention to the use of the elements of artistic thinking, which are included in the "Fine Art" lessons, in order to acquire a positive meaning for the changes in the child's mind. This situation means that the formation and step-by-step development of artistic thinking in schoolchildren is a continuous educational process, which is filled with content and developed at the stages of personal development .

Promoting theoretical knowledge to prepare future teachers of fine arts for the formation of elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren, working based on the above-mentioned psychological characteristics guarantees the success of pedagogical activities aimed at this goal. In addition, it is important that the person responsible for this work (teacher, class leader, etc.) has sufficient psychological and pedagogical knowledge and skills.

Researcher N. Yuldasheva stated that "in order to form the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren, it is necessary to develop communicative competences in the future teachers of visual arts, first of all, by studying their personal capabilities, psychological and physiological characteristics, and the interaction between representatives of the family, educational institution, the public, and the medical field."

In fact, artistic thinking is perfect when it is improved in a complex manner in organic connection with many components of personal qualities. Therefore, it is necessary to apply the principle of a comprehensive approach and create certain pedagogical conditions in preparing future teachers of fine arts to form elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren:

- 1) analysis of the practical situation of formation of elements of artistic thinking;
- 2) analysis of the development of elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren as a unique psychological-pedagogical phenomenon;
- 3) to approach the process of formation of the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren as a holistic didactic event of future visual arts teachers based on the identified indicators;
- 4) to achieve a description of the conclusions made in order to prepare the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren in certain forms, taking into account the characteristics of working with gifted students in the future.

One of the most important positive qualities of future art teachers is their attitude towards students. The attitude towards the students is the teacher's love for his profession. As the teacher interacts with his students, the main conditions that ensure his success in this area are related to his professional knowledge, universal and personal qualities.

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